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UPSURGENGE

A brief introduction is advisable in order to be clear in what way one upsurging field of awareness, for example music, can appear through another, a painting, storytelling or a public lecture. Chudovski, writing about Čiurlionis, points out that Čiurlionis painted his music and even his poetry. How can one field become a *calling*, creating an entire mood or atmosphere in which daily events, people and environment are encompassed by a different vision? It seems that we are confronted by an awareness called *synesthesia*. The term signifies a basic domain of overlapping and interpenetrating awareness in which one field, such as the visual field, is transcribed directly into another, such as audial or tactile. One sees loud, exciting, hot colors, hears angular and sharp voices, tactile, scary and encasing darkness. *Synesthetic* awareness opens an understanding of how a written text and visual art allow access to the voices, feelings, joys and anxieties of another culture, another time. This is evident in personality cults, for example those originating in the Middle East, where the will of the father written in stories, depicted in paintings, chanted in temples, or the promises of the son, heard after thousands of years. It is evident in the voices of shamans, or the resonances in a desert cave, commanding “repeat”, send millions into “holy wars”. Such events show a presence of awareness which does not have any specific features, although everything is pervaded by it as being in excess of every specific event, and yet present in our own daily encounter with and in indefinite ever-surging fields. This excess will be called in this presentation aesthetic and in some narrower sense, dimensional.

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Awareness

To explicate the aesthetic awareness of Čiurlionis or, more precisely, Čiurlionis as a lived aesthetic awareness, we can begin with our own in order to suggest the way we access his, or for that matter, those of others. No doubt, some would say that it is presumptuous to speak in the name of someone else’s awareness, but awareness, specifically that of Čiurlionis, is not some sort of “internal, private, psychological” affair, but open to the world as it is disclosed by himself and by others with whom he had close encounters. All these aspects comprise the

depth of his, just as well as our awareness, extended through his artwork and above all, his aesthetics. Before positing any culturally available personal designation as Ego or Self, we can claim that there is a field of upsurging presence that comprises a background for secondary phenomena which are selected, but whose very continuity does not exhibit any need for traditional designation as intentional; for precise phenomenology, this secondary level depends on **passive fusion** that allows specific perceptual aspects to form a continuous upsurgence which can become identifiable units. But it is obvious that a unit cannot be regarded as separate from the surging and shifting phenomena and from its depth. Here the term “dimension” might help. **The unclear shape of a fish or royals in a painting is coming into presence which is seen as not quite complete, but it traces this coming into presence out of dimension of depth. Through it, the artist sees the streaks of a bluish, gilded, vibrant surging and vanishing but never complete entity.** A warning is in order. The artist is not engaged as a subject who associates this emergence from the upsurging world with past experiences. Prior to memory, there is a passive fusion, even synesthetic depth which can never freeze into an entity. It is possible to disclose the appearance of the primal upsurgence of a field of presence in some specific aesthetic form – the awareness of others as they emerge in Čiurlionis daily life.

Traveling to other regions as Čiurlionis did, nations and civilizations are equivalent to going to meet friends and colleagues – to a place called Warsaw, where he enters a salon peopled by intellectuals and artists sponsored by Madam Walman. She is interested in the works of Čiurlionis, praises them and even buys them. Meeting her again and again, he encounters her not just as this being, but sees her as “the same” through the changes as the depth trajectory of his work, exhibited in her salon for the various guests of different cultures. Many views are paraded by the guests, intense dialogue on most diverse fields, leading Čiurlionis to read great works of and about art, philosophy, history, other strange worlds of India found in Ramayana, the life of Krishna, Nietzsche and Kant, traveling great cities and regions, where melodious mountains, sheep herds and clouds trace the sky – each forming a synesthetic emerging field of awareness which is not only a **constant upsurgence, but also antiphonic.** After all, Kant and Nietzsche are part of his awareness, and thus intersecting

aesthetic theories cannot form a harmony. That is why the principle feature of any field of awareness is its upsurge with great options for some feature, including a person to constantly, but, due to the depth, never appear completely. In this sense, Čiurlionis encounters his hostess as a depth of his own awareness without ever encompassing that depth just as she, despite her constant encounter with him, her appreciation of his art and its greatness, can never say, „I know him or his work completely.“ **Their mutual presence has “thickness” – a dimension - or even density which does not yet include any memories or future aspects. It is purely a presence of a “field of flux” without orientations.** In this sense, it maintains itself in a passive way as originary upsurge of a field that cannot be denied without denying the ground of all other layers of selective perception, such as discussing Wundt’s psychology, or Sita of Ramayana. We note that neither stasis nor flow, neither simultaneity nor sequence or any other time metaphor can be attributed to it. Its morphology can be expressed as a wide range of perceptual configurations which was called antiphony where there is not yet a direction, where sounds rush from silence all at once, where the antiphonic upsurge, the primal field, does not exhibit any temporal or other characteristics.

This is obvious in the numerous encounters with another, for example Madam Walman. Through her changes there is a thickness – a depth - which not only includes her, but those others present in her salon, forming their own depth through their dialogues and an identity that does not exhibit any boundaries, and yet cannot be subsumed by her and the others, just as he cannot encompass their depth appearance; they allow Čiurlionis to continuously form a passive fusion which thickens the depth without exhausting its field as antiphonic. In anticipation of further discussion, we take for granted that the present is the field without characteristics of things yet out of which the latter upsurge without ever finally exiting the depth phenomena. In every encounter with Madam Walman, her look has a thickness and it lurks in depth of the new hairdo, the different touch, the streaks in her hair and a little droop under her chin. **And precisely this transparency, disclosing the thickness, allows Čiurlionis to see her as “the same”. In all cases, the awareness includes “the same”. The present encounter opens in antiphonal distance juxtaposed aspects which are present as temporal**

depth. He does not first meet a different looking stranger and then traverse in his memory numerous past images in order to settle on the most probable one. There is never a doubt that this is Madame Walman, despite the apparent fact that she has changed, and this change discloses itself immediately to him, not yet as a recollection from the present, but as given all at once. What is unique about her presence in depth is that he paints a work for her, not as a traditional portrait, but as an aesthetic work – and of course does not include himself.

Meanwhile Madam Walman is the living embodiment in the totality of the depth of his living awareness. Of course this awareness is only his and she cannot be reduced to that awareness. This is to say she is for herself completely irreducible to what she is for him. She is a trace of his temporal thickness, while in her awareness, she is her own depth through him. Thus, the trace she is throws him back upon himself and his own living awareness. This might seem to be solipsistic in the modern philosophical sense, but the very uniqueness she possesses and her appearance in the living awareness of Čiurlionis, her being irreducible completely to his experience of her, breaks the solipsistic mode. In brief, what appears in the field of perception has a resiliency that cannot be absorbed and in turn created by a solipsistic subject. The living awareness, as an upsurge, is not a fortuitous creation of a solipsistic ego. The mode of appearance of what is given in the living awareness is an opacity against which awareness opens up and can never be satisfactorily completed. This may be seen in the seeming incompleteness of the figures in his paintings and even in his music. The correlate to her obscurity or opacity shows up to the extent that her visible aspects are the ones appearing under the light that he provides, the light that is equally opaque. As a living awareness, he has a vector or a moment of refraction that is uniquely his and thus allows him to account for his ambiguity of others, his inability to have a complete transparency of her presence and also the presence of others in the salon. After all, they are opening depths of still others, such as scientists, philosophers and artists. Thus in a direct and concrete encounter, there is never a completion that would give us all at once what the other is, or what we are. **This means that to a certain extent there occurs a creation of awareness, to a certain extent, since the resiliency of what is present in the other and ourselves delimits the range of what can**

be incompletely completed. That is the reason why the disclosure of his own depth by all the others is not a completion of such a depth. And again as a trace of his thickness in depth, they are inadequate and lack the necessary complement to fulfill his surging awareness through which he “filters” their presence, and in turn, he cannot fully pervade their awareness, although both disclose a world depth which appears for what it is: an openness which can be shaded as emptiness or silence, and in metaphysical terms even as nothingness. In other words, the surging awareness reveals a depth not only of one life, but, in the traces of the other, exhibits the presence of generations.

The living awareness discloses the antiphonic field and the manner in which selected aspects become “transparent in depth”. The latter can be explicated in Čiurlionis’ presence of his beloved. More than any other person, she shades his life with Eros and Kama, and that is a way of disclosing the inescapable attractions of the world. In keeping with the theme of awareness, she is an embodiment of the ungraspable and yet passionate world itself. An immediate confusion must be avoided: *It is not due to his erotic passion for her like some sort of psychological feeling that the world suddenly appears erotic and attractive, that everything is shaded by gentleness; she is the way that Čiurlionis discovers the expressive dimensions of the cosmos – the gentleness of colors and the furies of the sea. To speak with the classics of the West and India, a specific figure captures and discloses the cosmic fire, passion and play. Her gentle look, a touch of hand, is also a mother’s touch of his childhood, a Lithuanian harmony, and a world at peace – before memories – the upsurge of her image is also a depth of his passionate life, committed to understand the creation and continuous self-creation of the world.*

It might be argued that such awareness of one’s depth through others is not concretely perceptual and consists only of the play of imagination and memories of long gone past events. After all, on a temporal line, we are at the now point, and every other awareness is either projection or recollection. Yet it can be shown that prior to memory even perceptual awareness of something is not only vivid, but has a depth which might be more vivid than the so-called temporal present. The description of such depth is explicated through various instances that are most vivid, indeed as vivid as any perceptual presence. With the upsurge of the present field, there perceptions surge without active

recollection, without being asked to appear, and without a thematic focus retained through acts of recollection. The perception of taste, the appearance of childhood events in meeting with the Lithuanian community in Petersburg, the bite of dark bread, in its direct taste, reveals no vague recollection in memory of past events, but a presence in full intensity which now almost succeeds in eliminating from the horizon of the living all other perceptual aspects. But what is lived “again” with full intensity is an instance lived “already”, and yet it appears with the features as if lived for the first time.

The direct perceptual difference between the upsurging awareness and the normal memory shows up in the way that such awareness can contain perceptions that can almost supplant the presently given thickness by another. Only the incessant presence of the primary perceptual upsurge as a field with non-thematic horizons prevents a total eclipse of such a field by the perceptual depth to become all that there is. The irreducible horizons allow the experimenter to concurrently signify the directly perceived “depth events” with the psychological term memories. In this sense, Čiurlionis can be directly aware that what has taken place is the recapturing of a part of his own lived experience.. Such a recapturing, by virtue of being the same, even if signified as again, demonstrates the repetition, under specific conditions of the lived awareness and thus its non-temporality, if by temporality is meant the physical flow of events which never come back – insisted upon by the sciences. But in the living present, where a perceptual moment upsurges with involuntary images, the past is relived and recaptured and, for this awareness, time is reversed.

In all respects, the depth phenomena is the depth of the world with all of its sparkling features. If we speak of any topic, we find that it opens a field of awareness which sweeps up friends and foes who aid and disrupt our own thinking, tastes and understanding. To speak of reason, we sense the presence of Socrates and Plato, and also Kant and Nietzsche, to mention freedom, we trace the depth of vast theologies and damnation, to have a glass of wine is to be in Barcelona. **But the depth is not the past, just as the Big Bang is not some event which occurred and is no longer. After all, it is still coming from the cosmic depth and will touch our instruments with spectacular fireworks – and is completely independent from our short-term memories, although announced**

by Ptolemaic Epicycles, Galileo's telescope, Newton's apple, Einstein's aesthetics, and metaphysical quests for the "beginning and origin".

The awareness depicted so far is a way of speaking about the awareness of art in the works of Čiurlionis. It is the way that figures emerge and float, assume a fusion and even synesthetic resonances without completion – e.g. Rex. Such figures can even be given symbolic reading, storylines, even vocabulary – the sea, the forest, the archer, and many others, and in music, the nocturnal sonata, etc. As pointed out, in all awareness there are these passive fusions and art critics pay attention to their features – although without attending to their depth or thickness. Čiurlionis, of course, takes recourse to direct awareness and shows how they emerge, fuse, but never as things or objects. This requires a slow and careful consideration of another mode of transparency disclosing silent dimensions pulsating through figures and objects as artwork.

Dimensions

Lest we be misled by some accounts of awareness as an empirical generalization of some sequence of impressions, we shall not be able to account for what Čiurlionis depicts. Let us take some familiar examples from social life and literature which might clarify such excess. An example from literature, such as Zola, is instructive. Starting with general impressions, we find Zola's writing to be composed of themes and figures which are reduced to carnality. Zola does not seem to be engaged in any scientific explanation, but has elevated the basic life world into a literary principle. He parades brute and blind instincts, carnal love and the base side of human nature. He is interested in the animal within the human. He distorts the human visage to look like an animal. Thus *Nana*, a beautiful animal, is irresistible due to the power of her sex, an earthy Venus with coarse legs. She is simply a crude adventure of flesh minus progress or tragedy, evil or good; she is basic. But what of the non-basic, the seemingly virtuous; in some other works, such as *Bonheur des Dames* or *Joie de Vivre*, where Denise is not a heroine torn between vast choices and tragic decisions; she is simply healthy. In *Pauline*, it is not her will that wins, but her health. They are basic forces that have no other purpose except being a flat statement that this

is the way life is. All that once was seen as noble and grand, all figures that once dominated the literary scene, the romantic, the heroic, the very Oedipal, are either replaced or reduced to something that is most primitive and direct. This dimensional excess is paraded in current numerous films, television shows, advertisements, where the thighs, bare bottoms, protruding tops are paraded under diverse guises: beauty pagents, Ninja warriors, pop-music, sex cells everything, Wonder Woman, Schwarzenegger, and countless others, including ethics reduced to libidinal sublimation. As a matter of awareness, this carnal dimension is never given in any definition, yet it pervades the definitions of all events – before empirical generalization.

Even the major expressive dimension – passion for life – available as Eros, Kama, Fire, and all their attendant variants of terror, attraction, repulsion, creation and destruction, appeared throughout history and reached our day in a somewhat diminished stature as eroticism and sexuality. While there are voices proclaiming that Eros and mythos are relics, residua of unenlightened ages, residua which are finally swept aside by the light of scientific reason and the understanding of the biological functions of life, its reduction to this state is evidence of its pervasive presence. Thus, the Western-philosophical direction, initiated by Platonic quest for metaphysics, gives Eros a vertical movement – transcendent style, while Vesya in India, deploys Kama in horizontal fashion, without the need of transcendence toward art forms in another world. *Yet in both cases, there is a common understanding that Eros/Kama passion is a presence that envelopes, pervades, and stylizes art. As mentioned, Čiurlionis is captivated by the erotic passion appearing through his beloved, but also present both as a layer on and pervasive through the passions of the sea and the solar efulgence which is not reducible to the sunlight. The efulgence just as the Eros/Kama are aesthetic, even if revealed by the sunlight.*

Art and Aesthetic

The aesthetic are the immediately sensuous dimensions that envelope, pervade and condition the ways that the presence of things or events obtain their visibility and audible styles. The sensuality is the primal shading of the upsurgent

world and is disclosed by artistic figures which, while visible and audible, spread the aesthetic. For example, in mythological stories the divine Aphrodite is a figure, but she is a disclosure of the gentleness of the entire region, while Artemis is the stormy wildness. For Greeks this dimension was the beautiful. The aesthetic, the shining forth in the formation of art, must be distinguished from the “perceptual” as a characterization of a formed thing, a color, a quality, a sound of something. This is art with all of its symbolic values ascribed to forms. **But the aesthetic is the immediately given, the enveloping sensuous dimensionality prior to a given chromatic or sonorous articulation. The shining forth, the golden day, the toning of the silence in the Zen bell, the nocturnal moonlight, are not phenomena as appearances of things in their shape, but the very phenomenality of phenomena, the silent tonality of music, the enveloping resonance of solitary sounds.** The phenomenality is a trace of some other, perhaps the most uncanny, presence. This presence was accepted by most diverse philosophers and artists, shamans and mystics, the Maha-Kali and star wisdom of various traditions which strove to capture in word, rite, rapture this sensuous phenomenality as if it were the very emergence of Being, of figures, things, an emergence which was and is never complete. If one ponders all First Philosophies raising the question of the origin of the phenomena of the world, one discovers that all attempts to allow this origin to emerge is only partial and always pulled back into the presence of pervasive, encompassing dimensions which do not characterize anything. We hope to discover that these dimensions are the appearance of the world in whose elusive envelopment and compass all things come to unifying and dispersing manifestation into their depth - totally present in the art and aesthetics of Čiurlionis.

Obviously the world here is faceless, since it is not an entity possessing appearances to some conscious or even subconscious self, but the way its silent sway lends all things and their being manifestation and sheen, resonance and depth – their emergence without completely leaving the aesthetic. The ancient Greeks celebrated this essential encounter with the world by sacrificial acts in order to glimpse at the *apeiron as aisthesis*, not as some formless stuff or some particles out of which all things come and are formed, and to which all things dissolve and return, but a trace of the world’s depth. This reading is suggested

by the fact that the *apeiron* cannot be infinite; it simply breaks limits without foreboding infinity. This is precisely what appears between the infinite - whatever it may be - and the temporal, between the essential presence of worldly time and serial time; it is the *aistheton*. It brings to presence the fleeting and unrepeatable expressivity of a face, a rhythm, where the human gesture attains essential singularity. Such singularity is the most fleeting, as are the sounds of nocturnal sonatas, and it is the fleeting which is required to capture the depth of a figure. What one notes is that such an essential gesture, the inspiring of the keyboard by Čiurlionis as an act, is not a trace either of sequential or cyclical time. The essential gesture disrupts the common prejudgments by lived time. This concept is designed to circumvent the reflexive paradoxes that dominated the curiosity of the literate all the way from Plato through Russell, and indeed those revealed long ago by Nagarjuna. **What Čiurlionis offers as a solution is not based on logical thinking, even if he explores the latter, but on the aesthetics of intelligence**, captured in art-aesthetics and not philosophy, science, psychology or sociology. Arts, and in Čiurlionis' aesthetics, the cosmic passion has done a more credible job in light of its very medium: the aesthetic. The latter are the dimensions which were relegated traditionally to subjective phenomena and not the real. Hence *tiempo vivo*, the lived, the pre-reflective awareness, lends itself to the aesthetic and not the metaphysical. It is the aesthetic that has also been denigrated to be merely an appearance, designated to serve metaphysics, theology and ontology. The latter deal with objects and things, while the aesthetic plays with the dimensional – not as another appearance of things, but as a cosmic condition for the appearance of the very origin of all things and its envelopment in the cosmic phenomena. **In principle, the power of Čiurlionis' aesthetics is not that he creates such dimensions, but lives and exhibits them. He is not an external observer or listener, but a continuation and co-creation with their upsurgence.**

Yet precisely the phenomenality of the surging formations that comprise the aesthetic envelopment is more lived than conceived. This lived time, then, may be shaded as a dimension out of which some event assumes a shape and visage, a silence disrupted and continued as another resonating silent dimension, a surge that crisscrosses our own receptivity. The surge of silent dimension

in voluminous colors – equally tracing the silent depth, are events without chronological points. And such dissolution of chronology is expressed at times by the term *atemporal* as a mark of dislocation over that of never completed identity. What this opens is a dissolution of materiality and even substantiality in favor of an emerging present as an event and as a structuration that moves between any definable entitative person, event and some purely transcendent origin – even if the latter appears as a figure. **Čiurlionis depicts such figures as surging, as an exodus, but never completely independent.** This context is the present that cannot be split logically; it is experienced not objectively or subjectively, but precisely as the framing in flux, where one finds an indistinction between past as present, future as present and the present as past.

The hint, then, at the primacy of activity, forming-shaping upsurging figures, whether they are a fish or stars, kings or petals, out of the aesthetic comprises the first moment in any regard of any artwork. This is the sensuous present that is not yet articulated into time phases and comprises the pathic moment that originates the movement of creativity. In this origination, regions are delimited, and thinking, language and things assume a possibility of orientation and failure. Thus, prior to the language of things, there appears an articulating-articulated activity that is tensed with, spreads, and is equally an extension of the aesthetic envelopment. And the ways of its appearance are at once origination and self-founding, and comprise a constant coming into presence, a constant origination. **Aesthetic awareness and its unrepeatability is premised on the participation in the surging aesthetic passion that is self-warranting, a creation as self-creation, a passion that is impassioned with itself – not some subjective, but world passion. The passion of the surging sea and the resisting forests in Čiurlionis' works.** It is, after all, this origination that first allows the emergence of delimitations required for relationships and the formation of similarities and differences. An aesthetic formation, inscribing a particular space-time style cannot be exhausted and located. Not a single formation, not even classical arts with their graphic and even grammatical contours allow themselves to be reduced to a picture of something with its boundaries. *At the outset it is graspable in its exodus and, as was articulated by Indian aesthetics, the explosive transgression of limitations and*

hence a disclosure of the cosmic passions, cosmic pathic moment which captures and encompasses the artist. In this sense, the theories of aesthetics, consisting either of analytic or dialectic of art works and our attitudes toward them, have not dealt with the aesthetic origination as it takes place in its own self-supporting and self-forming dimensions so visible - audible in all that Čiurlionis creates. **The art-aesthetic of Čiurlionis is not only a disclosure of the upsurgence of the ever self-creating cosmos, but also his participation in such self-creation. He continues the self-creation of the universe.**

This origination is precisely what constitutes a receptivity in the heart of the aesthetic. The receptivity does not consist of the reflective return of a subject to itself, for it is neither reflection nor an objectivity of self toward itself. The subject of aesthetic is not a solitary subject projecting and grasping a world of transcendence and Čiurlionis related to the transcendence, but an originating attunement to and within the presence and envelopment of the aesthetic. The latter opens up his sensuality for his opening of it. The aesthetic is opened and opens receptively. One becomes insofar as something happens, and it happens insofar as one becomes. This is noted with Zen awareness where the artist becomes insofar as the cosmos becomes by way of the artist. Thus we can speak of color fields not qualifying anything, yet out of which emerge figures in their exodus without leaving those fields; after all, they shade across the emerging figures. **By way of this aesthetic, Čiurlionis is enveloped by a world which permits him to upsurge with his artwork. The pathic is an original constitution of awareness that is equally dimensional. When Čiurlionis shades the forest and the sea in blue, he means more than the color of the sea or the blue surging, enveloping and laying over with sparkling sounds over and through the emerging "forest and sea", just as his gold shaded works expose the golden tone of the shimmering cosmos from which appear his castles and shapes.** One does not encounter some descriptive color of things to present the color tone of the emerging shapes. Rather in the aesthetic color tones the world clings, resonates, to the extent that Čiurlionis himself inhabits color clinging world tonality which has not yet rigidified into a figure. Here, the pathic moment is not yet a feeling of a subject, but a task to be articulated in a style. The latter is the way one reaches the pathic moment of our engaged receptivity: a shake up

of the trusted world of things and objects as finished and independent entities. **It is the *perversamente, the perversmas* that Čiurlionis has understood so well. There is a *terra nova* that is older than the things and the illumination of their being.** It is an attunement of the overlapping of the sense fields, and the constitution of their primordial depths prior to location and sequence. This is to say, the movement of the artwork is a non-oriented *dynamis* that does not possess a predetermined form to be brought out, and any emerging form never becomes completely other from the aesthetic envelopment.

A chromatic field was deemed to be a medium of expression, thought and feeling, having numerous symbolic possibilities as audiovisual metaphors; all of this misses what Spanish call the *esplendores indefinidos*, the indefinite splendor which breaks the contours of any restriction. It is the transcendence of things, and yet without becoming either metaphysical or mythical. The *esplendores indefinidos* provides both the phenomenality-audiality that allows us to see and hear. The aesthetic sets the mood of perception and articulates the possibilities of variation in depth. In this sense, form is not a delimitation, but a boundary among aesthetic dimensions, an active pivot or an axis that is suggested by intersecting and overlapping aesthetic dimensions, as well as intimating novel ways of intersecting, overlapping and modulating. No doubt, when one moves to the aesthetic as color or sound, one discovers it to be embedded with a multitude of symbolisms. Greek symbolisms of blue, Hebrew symbolisms of white and red, etc. Such symbolisms merely detach the quality, the perceptual side of things and invests them with a variety of cultural meanings. Yet the aesthetic is much broader, more encompassing, in whose vastness and depth things remain the same but the same in depth – as discussed in the introductory section.

Take the whiteness suggested by Melville: beyond its traditional symbolic attachments, it evokes the indefinite, the immensity of the cosmos. It is the foreboding, uncanny, the unsettling, because it is not actually inherent in substance, but only laid on as if from within and without. And yet this laying on transfixes all things, and the pallor of lepers appears only in this whiteness, wherein not a thing shines upon their faces, but an enveloping, insubstantial dimension. And the latter is not a sum of white colored figures. It is impersonal and oblivious to individuality. One cannot place it in perspective because one

is within it. The only ways that traditional arts dealt with it was by investing it with symbolic meanings, by humanizing the aesthetic, by attaching it to recognizable things and substances. **Here we find Melville's "The Whiteness of the Whale", the white whiteness, at times as an absence of any color. It is not a perceived color, but an absence, since it is not a color of anything, and yet not a nothing.** This aesthetic is what is tensed with a spatial-temporal pulse that can slacken, intensify and yield the positions and places to all things such that the latter become the media of vision, shaded by the phenomenality-audiality of the aesthetic.

Such a tonality is given not only with the white or any specific chromatic dimension, but also with darkness that is the color which is equally an open dimension that has no color from which all things emerge; it is the dimension of surging formations, where everything assumes an aesthetic mood. **The darkness, experienced in the depth of the night, is shaded by black, but the darkness is enveloping, and regardless of how far one moves, the darkness does not disappear – it is not a color of something, but an aesthetic depth out of which things surge and sink away, shaded by a color which cannot be named. It is the synesthetic question that Pocahontas asked the white man: Have you heard the coyote howling in the moonlight?** The nocturnal silence is disclosed by a moonlight shaded coyote's sound which surges and colors the silent night with a depth - Čiurlionis' Nocturnal Sonata. **We have a grammatical habit to attribute the aesthetic to something; for example, we say "the sky is blue" or the "night is dark", without noting that there is no entity called sky or night.** They are dimensions, just as the moonlight which is not at all the color of the moon, although one is captured by its "magnetic" surge through the resonating night. Let us note that for Čiurlionis, the sky is not above, a cover with diverse colors, dotted by clouds; we are in it from our feet up, and we can be the archer in Čiurlionis' painting who is in the sky and shaded by the day which is equally not a thing with a color – although all colors are diurnal.

The specific color tone of a thing is a phenomenon that manifests the phenomenality of the aesthetic as a dimensional trace of the world. **In various paintings of Čiurlionis, the yellow is not the building; it is an aesthetic**

dimension revealing what Čiurlionis wanted to do: trace the world in his figures. Yellow ceases to be a color of anything specific, such as a given shade of yellow sun or buildings; it is equally prior to symbolic investments, prior to meaning. Just as blue of the waves shimmering through the forest is laid over across the surging waves, but not the color of the emerging waves. Indeed, such a color tone is given to receptivity as an attunement to surging cosmos, and the shimmering contours of the artist's strokes and gestures that separate and overlap shades upon shades, continuously emerging with clinging resonances - resonating synesthetically across all receptivities. The presence of a shimmering depth and overlapping shadings comprise the deepening of the synesthetic into cosmic memory - in the artwork and its aesthetics as traces of the surging, self-creation of the world.

To the gentle eye the stillness reveals itself pervaded with shining. But the stillness of the world is not an empty silence, just as much as rest is not a simple lack of motion. The stillness has its wondrous voice which is music. When Čiurlionis inspires the keyboard, the original worldly silence resounds. Silence is dimensional; it is not an object that can be signified; the sound, inspired by Čiurlionis, does not signify either; it traces the silent toning both as musicality and as depth. The silence is not an object; it is all pervasive and may equally lend the toning its visibility, such as the *golden tone* of the day. Yet the toning also traces a way of silence which, while articulated does not separate into some characterizable components. The very characterization of such components would be equally tracing the toning as a way of silence and sheen. What appears here is the toning that can be traced by a sound, by a voice, experienced as an all-pervasive domain required of poetic speaking. In turn, the poetic speaking traces the way of the silent toning as the split between color-sound and the surging world.

Presence

The aesthetic phenomena of the artwork that trace the *aistheton* in its shimmering resonances as the phenomenality of the phenomena - a phenomenality that comprises the trace of the world - are equally the background of transgression

of the human time of sequentiality. Such aesthetic phenomena are a way of revealing the pathic moment comprising an intractable presence of the world. Cezanne suggests that colors comprise a swinging of color logic that dissolves the dull stark geometry. I see in spots. And thus for him, a new time epoch has broken in: the true. There are colors and the bright shimmer across them, intimating an intimacy with the presence of the world. The swinging flight from the Earth to the Sun, this self-streaming of colors comprises as well the traces of the *aistheton* that is equally an open cosmos. The authenticity of an artwork consists in tracing the gesture of the flight in equilibrium without robbing it of its swinging. The aesthetic here relates depths and breadths prior to geometric metaphors. As Claudel suggests, the color possesses all power of resonating from the moment when it ceases to describe objects and becomes constituted by its presence as aesthetic, as a trace of a cosmic surge. There is no empty space time continuum, no box that frames events; space-time is incessantly shaded and traced by resonances of the aesthetic, while it in turn, is traced by the color tones that resonate depths of cosmic memories and styles prior to sequential temporality, history or eternity.

It nonetheless should be noted that the phenomenality of the phenomena is not the visible aesthetic, nor is it the invisible vectors of signification that cradle every artistic figure. Art does not return us to the visible or audible; it makes visible tonality, the coming into play of the relationship of the breadth and depth of the aesthetic dimensions, their overlapping and lending themselves to visible tonality of the artwork. In Borges' writing there is the aesthetic ambience, depicted chromatically, that does not signify any particular entity, reality, or image. The colors transcend visual, tactile and oral perception without ceasing to resonate, to be present. Thus apart from colorful depictions of things, one offers chromatic intimations that shimmer with resonances in a retroactive way to intersect and flood the emergent mundane things, a way that constitutes the pathic moment of world thinking. This is artistic genius. It seems that good artists are tracing some other dimensions than the presence and relationships of things. In the presence of the aesthetic, things acquire depth and not circumspection. **In this depth we sense the moonlight colors of the hyena, but also the depth of its being - proliferated indefinitely and opened**

in the depth of resonating chromatic variations, leading to a diffusion that finally defies any thing's color qualification. The moonlight-colored hyena's howl is present across dimensions that seem to defy any and all linguistic and literal categories. There is a good reason for that, even if we exclude the presumption that in daylight things look normal – normal only in the depth of daylight.

When one speaks of the color of moonlight, or that an archer was the color of the sunlight, and the hyena the color of the moonlit night, one cannot presume that such depictions are symbolic. This is to say, the moon is a thing, while color is a symbol, i.e. subjective, given only to perception. Such a reading still rests on language as a mirror, a representation, where mirrors mirror mirrors, and the metaphysics of Being and Nothing. It misses the sway of the aesthetic that transcends the essential delimitations and is primarily worldly, dimensional, amorphous, a presence that is impossible to deconstruct. In this sense, deconstructionism can only deal with metaphysics and not with the world. This is to say, the aesthetic “matters” to things, even in case of the claims that the colorless yellow of Čiurlionis' Rex does not matter to the emergent „royalty“. The latter term ought not suggest an essence, but an aesthetic depth that can shade into moonlight resonances in the “voices of the night” – all disclosing depth of the worldliness of the hyena as a depth of dangerous events that do not end up in a particular “essential” figure, although it is the cosmic depth of any figure. And this is the case which Čiurlionis experienced in the figures he encountered in their depth and aesthetic wonder.

Algis Mickūnas

IŠSILIEJIMAS

Santrauka

Turime paminėti, kad vienas suvokimo laukas, kaip pavyzdžiui, muzika, gali atsirasti per kitą – paveikslą, pasakojimą ar paskaitą. Chudovskis, rašydamas apie Čiurlionį, atkreipia dėmesį, kad Čiurlionis tapė savo muziką ir net poeziją. Kaip tariant, viena sritis gali atverti kitą sritį, sukuriant nuotaiką, atmosferą ar viziją, kuri apimtų kasdienius įvykius, žmones ir aplinką? Atrodo, kad mes susiduriame su sąmoningumu, vadinamu sinesteze. Šis terminas reiškia pagrindinę persidengiančio ir įsiskverbiančio suvokimo sritį, kurioje vienas laukas, pavyzdžiui regėjimo, transkribuojamas į kitą, pavyzdžiui į garsinį ar lytėjimo. Regime garsias, jaudinančias, karštas spalvas, girdime kampuotus ir aštrius balsus, mus apima baisi ir įtraukianti tamsa. Sinestetinis suvokimas atveria supratimą, kuris, kaip ir rašytinis tekstas ar vizualus menas leidžia suvokti kitos kultūros balsų prasmę, jų jausmus, džiaugsmus ir nerimą. Tai akivaizdu ir asmenybės kultuose, pavyzdžiui, kilusiuose iš Artimųjų Rytų, kur pasakojimuose aprašoma, paveiksluose vaizduojama, šventyklose giedama tėvo valia arba sūnaus pažadai, kurie skamba net ir po tūkstančių metų. Tą regime ir šamanų ištarose, išgyvenimuose patiriamuose dykumos oloje, ar įsakmiuose „pasikartojimuose“, siunčiant milijonus į „šventuosius karus“. Tai atveria sąmoningumą, kuris neturi jokių specifinių bruožų, tačiau persmelkia viską, kiekvieną konkretų įvykį tarsi iš aukščiau, ir pasireiškia kasdieniuose susidūrimuose su neapibrėžtais, nuolat augančiais laukais. Šis perteklius šiame tekste bus laikomas estetišku, o tam tikra siauresne prasme – išraiškos dimensija.

Raktažodžiai: M. K. Čiurlionis, sąmoningumas, sinestezė, estetika, estetinė gelmė, esatis, esaties laukas, plūsmas, pasyvus susilieėjimas, ekspresyvi dimensija.